

Formation of Heteropoly Acids by the Interaction of Vanadic Acid and Phosphoric Acid

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Vanadic acid, prepared by using ion-exchange resin from a metavanadate solution, is found to react with orthophosphoric acid, yielding two complex acids, one red having vanadium and phosphorus ratio as 2:1 and another colorless having the ratio as 1:3. The formation of the first one takes sufficient time, but the second one forms very quickly. Spectrophotometric measurements and Job's method of continued variation have been applied to elucidate the composition of the complexes. The stability constant and the free energy change are respectively 8.163×10^4 and 6.57 kcal./mole in the case of the red complex. The corresponding quantities for the colorless complex are 1.800×10^6 and 25.41 kcal./mole. The 2:1 complex shows maximum absorption at 500 μ , but the 1:3 complex shows nearly constant absorption over a range of 320-350 μ .

Formation of a number of heteropoly acids arising from acid anhydrides, namely, WO_3 , MoO_3 , or V_2O_5 , along with another acid (regarded in modern theory as furnishing the central atom or ion of the whole complex anion) is well known¹. Although a varying number of WO_3 , MoO_3 , or V_2O_5 molecules, e.g., 8, 9, 10, 11, and 12, may be combined with one central ion, there are, however, two types which are of particular importance because they occur frequently. These are 12 and 6 polyacids arising from the association of 6 or 12 acid anhydride groups (WO_3 , MoO_3 , or $V_2O_5/2$) with one central atom or ion. In the case of vanadic and phosphoric acids, there are mainly two types of complex acids². One type, known as the Perpureo series having the formulas $R_7[P(V_2O_6)_6]$ and $R_3H_2[PO(V_2O_6)_2]$, and the other, the Luteco compounds having the formulas $R[PO_2(VO_3)_2]$ and $R_2[PO_1(VO_3)]$. The only free acid that has been prepared has the formula $H_2[PO_3(VO_3)] \cdot 4H_2O$ and which crystallises in golden yellow plates.

The investigation of the composition of the heteropoly acids, formed by vanadic acid, has seldom been carried out using pure vanadic acid solution. Besides, spectrophotometric investigation of heteropoly-acid formation is very rare. The present authors have used pure vanadic acid solution, prepared by using H-ion exchange resin, and orthophosphoric acid as the starting materials and attempted to follow spectrophotometrically their interaction in an aqueous medium.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ammonium metavanadate of G.R. quality (E. Merck) was used for the preparation of the vanadic acid. The phosphoric acid used was also of the same quality. Amberlite IR-120(H), A.R. grade of Rhom & Haas Company, Pennsylvania, was used as the ion exchanger.

1. Job, *Ann. chim.*, 1926, z, 9, 113; *Compt. rend.*, 1926, 180, 928.

2. Emelius and Anderson, "Modern Aspects of Inorganic Chemistry", 1956, pp. 208-235.

3. Ephraim, "Inorganic Chemistry", 1954, p. 534.

A Beckman spectrophotometer, Model DU, and absorption cells of length 1 cm each were used for all absorption measurements. For all pH measurements a Cambridge Bench Type pH-meter was used.

Preparation of the Vanadic Acid and its Estimation

Vanadic acid, prepared from ammonium metavanadate, was purified in the same way as described earlier⁴.

Stoichiometry of the Complex.—The yellow vanadic acid, thus obtained, formed a red solution on addition of orthophosphoric acid to it. The formation of this colour was not instantaneous, but took appreciable time, depending on the concentration of the constituents used. An interesting phenomenon was observed in this connection. When phosphoric acid added was more than two equivalents of vanadic acid, not only this red colour ceased to appear but also the yellow colour of the vanadic acid began to disappear and when the proportion of phosphoric acid was still greater, a perfectly clear solution resulted. This observation indicated the probable formation of two complexes, one red and another colorless. The characteristics and the composition of these complexes have been studied.

Red Complex

Several mixtures of vanadic and phosphoric acids having ratios ranging from 20:1 to 1:1 were made. For each of these mixtures, blanks containing concentration of vanadic

○ & ⊕ refer to points for vanadic acid.
● & △ ,, ,, ,, mixtures of V and P.

acid as in the mixtures were also prepared. The absorption spectra of not a single mixture with water as blank yielded a maximum (vide Fig. 1). The only difference was that the absorption of each of the mixture at all the wave lengths used was greater than the corresponding blank. When, however, the optical densities, obtained by using the corresponding vanadic acid control as blank, were plotted against the wave lengths, a maximum at 500 mμ was obtained. Analogous curve could be drawn by subtracting the optical density of the pure vanadic acid from the optical density of the complex at each wave length of light used. Curves 1 and 2 of Fig. 2 illustrate this. Only one

maximum for each of the mixtures used was noticed, indicating presence of one coloured complex.

Curve 1 for V:P = 3:1. Curve 2 for V:P = 2:1.

● & △ represent calc. points and ⊕, expt. points.

FIG. 3

To find out the composition of the complex, the optical densities of the mixtures at 480 mμ and 500 mμ were measured and the difference between the optical densities of the complex and the corresponding vanadic acid solution was plotted against the mole fraction of the phosphoric acid. A peak at mole fraction 0.33 was found, indicating the formation of a complex when the ratio of vanadic acid to phosphoric acid was 2:1 (vide Fig. 3).

Colorless Complex

To study the second complex, mixtures containing vanadic acid and phosphoric acid having compositions ranging from 1:1 to 1:20 were prepared. For each of these mixtures, a blank containing the same concentration of vanadic acid as in the mixtures was also prepared. The absorption spectra of these mixtures were measured, but no maximum at any wave length used was observed. Only a short flat portion at about 280 mμ was found to occur (vide Fig. 5, curves 1-1' to 3-3'). When the difference between the optical densities of the mixtures and the corresponding vanadic acid controls was plotted against the wave lengths, a curve having more or less equal optical density difference for wave lengths ranging from 320 mμ to 350 mμ was obtained. This is illustrated in curves 1-3 in Fig. 4.

To find out the composition, the optical densities of each of these mixtures, subtracted from the corresponding blanks at 340 mμ, 350 mμ, and 360 mμ, were plotted against the mole fraction of phosphoric acid, when peaks at mole fraction 0.75 were found to occur. This indicates that the ratio of vanadic acid to phosphoric acid in the complex is 1:3 (vide Fig. 6). Mention should be made here that the formation of the red complex at the higher ratio of vanadium did not affect the optical density since its formation required considerable time at the concentration of the mixtures used (0.005M), whereas the colorless complex formed quickly and the measurements were taken within a short period.

FIG. 4

Curves 1 to 3 refer respectively to V:P mixture of 1:3, 1:5 and 1:10.

FIG. 5

1' to 3' refer respectively to V:P mixtures of 1:3, 1:5, and 1:10. 1 to 3 ,, to respective V conc.

Extinction Coefficients of Vanadic Acid and the Complexes

(a) *Vanadic Acid*.—Beer's law was found to hold good for vanadic acid over a wide range of wave lengths. The molar extinction coefficients, as calculated from the straight line obtained by plotting optical densities against concentrations, were 716.6, 658.5, 625.0, and 23.3 for 340 mμ, 350 mμ, 360 mμ, and 500 mμ respectively. The curves have not been shown for sake of brevity.

FIG. 6 O—At 340 mμ. ●—At 350 mμ. △—At 360 mμ.

(b) *Red Complex*.—The usual method of finding out the extinction coefficient from the measurement of optical density by assuming complete complex formation, when the ligand is added in large excess (more than ten times), could not be adopted in this case because of the fact that the complex changes into a different one when the ligand (phosphoric acid) is in excess. But in the reverse procedure, where a little phosphoric acid had been added to a large excess of vanadic acid, we assumed that the whole of the phosphoric acid had undergone complex formation and the extinction coefficient at any particular wave length could be found from the relation similar to that described earlier⁵.

$$\text{Total O.D.} = \epsilon [\text{vanadic acid}] - (2\epsilon - \epsilon') [\text{phosphoric acid}] \quad (1)$$

Knowing the extinction coefficient of the vanadic acid at any wave length, as mentioned previously, the extinction coefficient of the complex, ϵ' , was calculated from equation (1) for wave length $500 \text{ m}\mu$ and found to be 203.4.

(c). *Colorless Complex*.—In this case the ligand was kept in large excess (about 20 times) and the optical density was measured at several wave lengths. Assuming complete complex formation, the optical density was plotted against concentration of the vanadic acid at each wave length. From the curves obtained at all these wave lengths, the extinction coefficients were calculated from the slopes (vide Fig. 7). The values obtained for $340 \text{ m}\mu$, $350 \text{ m}\mu$, and $360 \text{ m}\mu$ were 164.0, 112.0, and 72.0 respectively.

FIG. 7

DISCUSSION

The results obtained confirm that the Leuteo compound of the formula $R [PO_2(VO_3)_2]$ having a bright yellow colour, reported by previous authors (*vide supra*), has the same composition as the red-coloured complex observed by us. Crystalline vanado-phosphates of the type V_2P has also been obtained by Chene⁶ by electrolysing V_2O_5 in fused alkali phosphate. Biltz⁷ has reported the existence of vanado-phosphate having vanadium to phosphorus ratio of 1:2, whereas the present authors have obtained evidence of the existence of a complex acid containing vanadium to phosphorus ratio as 1:3. Variation of conductance and pH was measured with the addition of increasing proportion of phosphoric acid. On plotting these data against the amount of phosphoric acid added, no break was noted.

Stability Constant

The red and the colorless complexes are both very stable. The stability constants are calculated in the following way.

6. *Compt. rend.*, 1939, 208, 1144.

7. *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1942, 249, 1.

(a) *Red complex*:

From equation (1), reported earlier⁵, and the extinction coefficient of the vanadic acid and of the complex, the concentration of the complex at a particular wave length for any vanadic acid and phosphoric acid ratio can be calculated. Then from equation (2) the stability constants can be calculated. The values of K , calculated for the ratios 5:1, 3:1, 2:1, and 1:1 at 500 $m\mu$ are 4.475×10^4 , 5.923×10^4 , 9.552×10^4 , and 4.697×10^4 respectively. Their mean value of 6.162×10^4 may be taken as the stability constant of the complex acid.

The free energy change of this reaction has been calculated from the equation:

$$-\Delta F = RT \ln K$$

and is found to be 6.573 kcal./mole at 25°.

(b) *Colorless complex*:

In this case also, the concentration of the complex can be calculated from equation (1)⁵ and hence the stability constant for any vanadic acid and phosphoric acid ratio. The values of K' at 1:2, 1:3, and 1:4 ratios have been calculated at 340 $m\mu$, 350 $m\mu$, and 360 $m\mu$ and are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

V:P ratio.	K' .	V:P ratio.	K' .	V:P ratio.	K' .
$\lambda=340 \text{ m}\mu$.		$\lambda=350 \text{ m}\mu$.		$\lambda=360 \text{ m}\mu$.	
1:2	1.195×10^9	1:2	1.119×10^9	1:2	2.032×10^9
1:3	1.718	1:3	1.814	1:3	2.415
1:4	1.947	1:4	1.814	1:4	2.235
Mean	1.620	Mean	1.682	Mean	2.227

The average of these mean values, 1.809×10^9 , may be taken to represent the stability constant of the 1:3 complex. The free energy change, $-\Delta F$, calculated by using this value of the stability constant, is 25.41 kcal./mole at 25°.

The probable composition of the 2:1 complex acid can be regarded as $H[PO_2(VO_3)_2]$ assuming tetra-co-ordination of the central atom P, due to Rosenheim⁸, in which two OH groups of the H_3PO_4 have been replaced by two VO_3 groups. But in the case of 1:3 complex acid, it is very difficult to reconcile it with the Rosenheim idea. Considering the role of vanadium as the central atom here, the metavanadic acid, HVO_3 , by taking three (HPO_4) groups in place of the three oxygen atoms, can probably form a complex acid of the composition $H[V(HPO_4)_3]$. Thus the vanadic acid and phosphoric acid react in the following manner:

and

Among the few chemical properties studied at present, the reaction of the red acid with the formation of a colorless solution with the addition of mineral acids, e.g., HCl, H_2SO_4 , HNO_3 , etc., but not with organic acids like CH_3COOH , has been observed. Neutralisation with alkali affords colorless salts. On shaking vigorously with ether, probably an ether addition compound is formed whereby the colour of the red acid disappears. The colorless complex acid, when shaken with ether, at first develops a red colour in the aqueous medium which slowly fades, leaving a faint violet colour to the ethereal layer. Investigations are in progress regarding these and other properties of these complex acids.

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